

Search string and searching strategy

Social Inequalities in Exposure to Ambient Air Pollution: An Update of Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis in the European Union Member Countries

1. OVID MEDLINE

Search run on 2024-5-23

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1      exp Air Pollution/      73067
2      exp Air Pollutants/    115744
3      exp Particulate Matter/ 82777
4      Vehicle Emissions/    12145
5      Traffic-Related Pollution/ 221
6      Ozone/18258
7      Sulfur Dioxide/6040
8      Carbon Monoxide/    19319
9      exp Fossil Fuels/    31571
10     ((air or ambient or atmospher*) adj3 (pollut$ or quality)).ti,ab,kf.    66486
11     (PM2* or PM10*).ti,ab,kf.    27419
12     (SO2 or NO2 or O3 or ozone or nitrogen dioxide or sulfur dioxide or carbon
monoxide).ti,ab,kf.    101392
13     fossil fuel$.ti,ab,kf.    8474
14     (Coarse particle* or Soot or Black smoke or Black carbon or Elemental carbon or
wood smoke).ti,ab,kf. 9843
15     ((vehicle$ or traffic) adj3 (emission$ or pollutant$)).ti,ab,kf. 5352
16     ((smog or fume$ or exhaust$ or diesel) and air).ti,ab,kf.    7724
17     ((emission* or air or atmospher*) adj2 (anthropogenic or motor or automobile* or car
or cars or road or power generation or indust* or combustion or smelting or construction or
demolition or burning or "chemical plant" or "chemical plants" or refiner* or residential or fire
or fires or ship or ships or locomotive or volcano or incinerator or smelter*)).ti,ab,kf.
10983
18     1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17
327126
19     exp Health Equity/    4306
20     exp Health Status Disparities/    20200
21     exp "Social Determinants of Health"/ 7311
22     Diversity, Equity, Inclusion/    383
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23 (inequit* or disparit* or inequalit* or disadvantage* or depriv* or vulnerab* or justice or
injustice or equity or equality).ti,ab,kf. 620086

24 ((socio* or social) adj1 (determinant* or differen* or factor*)).ti,ab,kf. 85475

25 exp sex factors/ 280477

26 exp Gender Equity/ 724

27 exp Gender Identity/ 28136

28 exp Women's Health/ 32447

29 exp homosexuality/ 36177

30 (gender-based or gender-related or "gender differences" or "gender factors").ti,ab,kf.
45751

31 (sex adj2 (role or difference? or factor? or inequit\$ or disparit\$ or inequalit\$)).ti,ab,kf.
77307

32 gender.ti,ab,kf. 433629

33 ((wom#n* or female*) adj1 role).ti,ab,kf. 1044

34 (m#n* adj1 role).ti,ab,kf. 10430

35 exp "Health Disparate, Minority and Vulnerable Populations"/ 176675

36 "Ethnic and Racial Minorities"/ 683

37 "Transients and Migrants"/ 14794

38 Minority groups/ 18785

39 Minority health/ 907

40 exp Ethnicity/ 110853

41 exp Racial Groups/ 107521

42 exp Refugees/ 13825

43 Race Relations/ 2460

44 Apartheid/ 58

45 Desegregation/ 17

46 exp Social Isolation/ 26567

47 Acculturation/ 7117

48 Cross-Cultural Comparison/ 28062

49 Cultural Characteristics/ 16889

50 Cultural Diversity/ 13119

51 exp disabled persons/ 75145

52 (disabled or disabilit* or handicap*).ti,ab,kf. 301330

53 Religion/ 16092

54 (ethnic\$ or race or racial or religio\$ or cultur\$ or minorit\$ or refugee* or refugit* or
indigenous or migrant* or immigr* or racism or transient*).ti,ab,kf. 2191498

55 exp Socioeconomic Factors/ 522490

56 Job Description/ 11175

57 exp Social Welfare/ 61637

58 Hierarchy, Social/ 2395

59 exp Social Dominance/ 7184

60 (socio-economic* or economic* or poverty or poor* or income or socioeconomic* or
socio\$economic* or occupation* or employ* or unemploy* or impoverished).ti,ab,kf.
2741557

61 Social Stigma/ 13670

62 Social capital/ 1740

63 Social Control/ 11996

64 exp Social Environment/ 129286

65 ((social* or socio* or psychosocial) adj2 (advantage* or disadvantage* or exclude* or exclusion or include* or inclusion or status or position or gradient* or hierarch* or class* or determinant* or discrimin* or condition or network* or connection or relation* or capital or cohes* or organis* or organiz* or context or support or influence)).ti,ab,kf. 286879

66 ((marriage or marital or civil) adj1 status).ti,ab,kf. 31381

67 exp Residence Characteristics/ 80374

68 Built Environment/ 1438

69 exp Home Environment/ 475

70 exp Ill-Housed Persons/ 11494

71 housing.ti,ab,kf. 40442

72 ((urban or rural or inner\$-city or slum or neighbo?rhood) adj2 (difference\$ or specific or analysis or inequit\$ or disparit\$ or inequalit\$ or depriv* or disadvantage*)).ti,ab,kf. 11861

73 ((residential or neighbo?rhood) adj2 environment*).ti,ab,kf. 4021

74 (homeless* or foreclosure* or eviction*).ti,ab,kf. 15989

75 (household adj2 size).ti,ab,kf. 2200

76 (schooling or illiterate or uneducated).ti,ab,kf. 15921

77 (school* adj1 duration*).ti,ab,kf. 48

78 ((higher or better or worse or less) adj2 (educated or education)).ti,ab,kf. 40215

79 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53 or 54 or 55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 61 or 62 or 63 or 64 or 65 or 66 or 67 or 68 or 69 or 70 or 71 or 72 or 73 or 74 or 75 or 76 or 77 or 78 6420743

80 exp "Europe"/ or exp "European People"/ or Europe.ti,ab,kf. or European.ti,ab,kf. or Europeans.ti,ab,kf. or "Alpine region*".ti,ab,kf. or "Alpine area*".ti,ab,kf. or "Alpine countr*".ti,ab,kf. or Baltic.ti,ab,kf. or Baltics.ti,ab,kf. or Balts.ti,ab,kf. or Estonia.ti,ab,kf. or Estonian.ti,ab,kf. or Estonians.ti,ab,kf. or Tallin.ti,ab,kf. or Latvia.ti,ab,kf. or Latvian.ti,ab,kf. or Latvians.ti,ab,kf. or Letts.ti,ab,kf. or Riga.ti,ab,kf. or Courland.ti,ab,kf. or Curonian.ti,ab,kf. or Curonians.ti,ab,kf. or Lithuania.ti,ab,kf. or Lithuanian.ti,ab,kf. or Lithuanians.ti,ab,kf. or Vilnius.ti,ab,kf. or Poland.ti,ab,kf. or Polish.ti,ab,kf. or Polska.ti,ab,kf. or Warsaw.ti,ab,kf. or Warszaw.ti,ab,kf. or Lemko.ti,ab,kf. or Lemkos.ti,ab,kf. or Lemkian.ti,ab,kf. or Lemkians.ti,ab,kf. or Lemk.ti,ab,kf. or Lemks.ti,ab,kf. or Pomerania.ti,ab,kf. or Pomeranian.ti,ab,kf. or Pomeranians.ti,ab,kf. or Silesia.ti,ab,kf. or Silesian.ti,ab,kf. or Silesians.ti,ab,kf. or Moravia.ti,ab,kf. or Moravian.ti,ab,kf. or Moravians.ti,ab,kf. or Bulgaria.ti,ab,kf. or Bulgarian.ti,ab,kf. or Bulgarians.ti,ab,kf. or Sofia.ti,ab,kf. or Thrace.ti,ab,kf. or Thracian.ti,ab,kf. or Thracians.ti,ab,kf. or Romania.ti,ab,kf. or Romanian.ti,ab,kf. or Romanians.ti,ab,kf. or Rumania.ti,ab,kf. or Rumanian.ti,ab,kf. or Rumanians.ti,ab,kf. or Bucharest.ti,ab,kf. or Bucuresti.ti,ab,kf. or Transylvania.ti,ab,kf. or Transylvanian.ti,ab,kf. or Transylvanians.ti,ab,kf. or Transilvania.ti,ab,kf. or Transilvanian.ti,ab,kf. or Transilvanians.ti,ab,kf. or Wallachia.ti,ab,kf. or Wallachian.ti,ab,kf. or Wallachians.ti,ab,kf. or Hungary.ti,ab,kf. or Hungarian.ti,ab,kf. or Hungarians.ti,ab,kf. or Magyar.ti,ab,kf. or Magyars.ti,ab,kf. or Budapest.ti,ab,kf. or Swabia.ti,ab,kf. or Swabian.ti,ab,kf. or Swabians.ti,ab,kf. or Slovakia.ti,ab,kf. or Slovak.ti,ab,kf. or Slovaks.ti,ab,kf. or Slovakian.ti,ab,kf. or Slovakians.ti,ab,kf. or Bratislava.ti,ab,kf. or Czech.ti,ab,kf. or Czechia.ti,ab,kf. or Czechs.ti,ab,kf. or Bohemia.ti,ab,kf. or Bohemian.ti,ab,kf. or Bohemians.ti,ab,kf. or Prague.ti,ab,kf. or Slovenia.ti,ab,kf. or Slovenian.ti,ab,kf. or Slovenians.ti,ab,kf. or Ljubljana.ti,ab,kf. or Balkan.ti,ab,kf. or Balkans.ti,ab,kf. or Balkanic.ti,ab,kf. or Croatia.ti,ab,kf. or Croatian.ti,ab,kf. or

Croatians.ti,ab,kf. or Dalmatia.ti,ab,kf. or Dalmatian.ti,ab,kf. or Dalmatians.ti,ab,kf. or Istria.ti,ab,kf. or Istrian.ti,ab,kf. or Istrians.ti,ab,kf. or Zagreb.ti,ab,kf. or Greece.ti,ab,kf. or Greek.ti,ab,kf. or Greeks.ti,ab,kf. or Hellenic.ti,ab,kf. or Athens.ti,ab,kf. or Crete.ti,ab,kf. or Cretan.ti,ab,kf. or Cretans.ti,ab,kf. or Cyclades.ti,ab,kf. or Cycladic.ti,ab,kf. or Dodecanese.ti,ab,kf. or Dodecanesian.ti,ab,kf. or Peloponnese.ti,ab,kf. or Peloponnesian.ti,ab,kf. or Peloponnesians.ti,ab,kf. or Cyprus.ti,ab,kf. or Cypriot.ti,ab,kf. or Cypriots.ti,ab,kf. or Cypriotic.ti,ab,kf. or Cypriote.ti,ab,kf. or Nicosia.ti,ab,kf. or Malta.ti,ab,kf. or Maltese.ti,ab,kf. or Valetta.ti,ab,kf. or Valletta.ti,ab,kf. or Gozo.ti,ab,kf. or Gozitan.ti,ab,kf. or Gozitans.ti,ab,kf. or Portugal.ti,ab,kf. or Portuguese.ti,ab,kf. or Portugueses.ti,ab,kf. or Lisbon.ti,ab,kf. or Madeira.ti,ab,kf. or Madeiran.ti,ab,kf. or Madeirans.ti,ab,kf. or Azores.ti,ab,kf. or Azorean.ti,ab,kf. or Azoreans.ti,ab,kf. or Macaronesia.ti,ab,kf. or Macaronesian.ti,ab,kf. or Macaronesians.ti,ab,kf. or Alentejo.ti,ab,kf. or Algarve.ti,ab,kf. or Spain.ti,ab,kf. or Spanish.ti,ab,kf. or Iberian.ti,ab,kf. or Iberians.ti,ab,kf. or Madrid.ti,ab,kf. or Balearic.ti,ab,kf. or Majorca.ti,ab,kf. or Majorcan.ti,ab,kf. or Majorcans.ti,ab,kf. or Mallorca.ti,ab,kf. or Mallorcan.ti,ab,kf. or Mallorcans.ti,ab,kf. or Menorca.ti,ab,kf. or Menorcan.ti,ab,kf. or Menorcans.ti,ab,kf. or Canary.ti,ab,kf. or Canarian.ti,ab,kf. or Canarians.ti,ab,kf. or Andalusia.ti,ab,kf. or Andalusian.ti,ab,kf. or Andalusians.ti,ab,kf. or Murcia.ti,ab,kf. or Murcian.ti,ab,kf. or Murcians.ti,ab,kf. or Valencia.ti,ab,kf. or Valencian.ti,ab,kf. or Valencians.ti,ab,kf. or Castilla.ti,ab,kf. or Castile.ti,ab,kf. or Castilian.ti,ab,kf. or Castilians.ti,ab,kf. or Castillian.ti,ab,kf. or Castillians.ti,ab,kf. or Leon.ti,ab,kf. or Leonese.ti,ab,kf. or Leoneses.ti,ab,kf. or Extremadura.ti,ab,kf. or Extremaduran.ti,ab,kf. or Extremadurans.ti,ab,kf. or Catalonia.ti,ab,kf. or Catalan.ti,ab,kf. or Catalans.ti,ab,kf. or Aragon.ti,ab,kf. or Aragonese.ti,ab,kf. or Navarre.ti,ab,kf. or Navarran.ti,ab,kf. or Navarrans.ti,ab,kf. or Basque.ti,ab,kf. or Basques.ti,ab,kf. or Cantabria.ti,ab,kf. or Cantabric.ti,ab,kf. or Cantabrian.ti,ab,kf. or Cantabrians.ti,ab,kf. or Asturias.ti,ab,kf. or Asturian.ti,ab,kf. or Asturians.ti,ab,kf. or Galicia.ti,ab,kf. or Galician.ti,ab,kf. or Galicians.ti,ab,kf. or Pyrenees.ti,ab,kf. or Pyrenean.ti,ab,kf. or Gibraltar.ti,ab,kf. or Gibraltarian.ti,ab,kf. or Gibraltarians.ti,ab,kf. or Italy.ti,ab,kf. or Italian.ti,ab,kf. or Italians.ti,ab,kf. or Rome.ti,ab,kf. or Apennine.ti,ab,kf. or Padane.ti,ab,kf. or Sicily.ti,ab,kf. or Sicilian.ti,ab,kf. or Sicilians.ti,ab,kf. or Sardinia.ti,ab,kf. or Sardinian.ti,ab,kf. or Sardinians.ti,ab,kf. or Aosta.ti,ab,kf. or Trentino.ti,ab,kf. or Piedmont.ti,ab,kf. or Piedmontese.ti,ab,kf. or Liguria.ti,ab,kf. or Ligurian.ti,ab,kf. or Ligurians.ti,ab,kf. or Lombardy.ti,ab,kf. or Lombard.ti,ab,kf. or Lombards.ti,ab,kf. or Lombardic.ti,ab,kf. or Veneto.ti,ab,kf. or Venetian.ti,ab,kf. or Venetians.ti,ab,kf. or Friuli.ti,ab,kf. or Emilia-Romagna.ti,ab,kf. or Emilian.ti,ab,kf. or Tuscany.ti,ab,kf. or Tuscan.ti,ab,kf. or Tuscans.ti,ab,kf. or Umbria.ti,ab,kf. or Umbrian.ti,ab,kf. or Umbrians.ti,ab,kf. or Marche.ti,ab,kf. or Latium.ti,ab,kf. or Abruzzo.ti,ab,kf. or Molise.ti,ab,kf. or Campania.ti,ab,kf. or Campanian.ti,ab,kf. or Campanians.ti,ab,kf. or Apulia.ti,ab,kf. or Apulian.ti,ab,kf. or Apulians.ti,ab,kf. or Basilicata.ti,ab,kf. or Calabria.ti,ab,kf. or Calabrian.ti,ab,kf. or Calabrians.ti,ab,kf. or France.ti,ab,kf. or French.ti,ab,kf. or Paris.ti,ab,kf. or Corsica.ti,ab,kf. or Corsican.ti,ab,kf. or Corsicans.ti,ab,kf. or Alsace.ti,ab,kf. or Alsatian.ti,ab,kf. or Alsatians.ti,ab,kf. or Aquitaine.ti,ab,kf. or Aquitain.ti,ab,kf. or Aquitan.ti,ab,kf. or Aquitans.ti,ab,kf. or Occitan.ti,ab,kf. or Occitans.ti,ab,kf. or Auvergne.ti,ab,kf. or Auvergnese.ti,ab,kf. or Brittany.ti,ab,kf. or Bretagne.ti,ab,kf. or Breton.ti,ab,kf. or Bretons.ti,ab,kf. or Burgundy.ti,ab,kf. or Burgundian.ti,ab,kf. or Burgundians.ti,ab,kf. or Loire.ti,ab,kf. or Ardenne.ti,ab,kf. or Normandy.ti,ab,kf. or Norman.ti,ab,kf. or Normans.ti,ab,kf. or Franche-Comte.ti,ab,kf. or Languedoc-Roussillon.ti,ab,kf. or Limousin.ti,ab,kf. or Azur.ti,ab,kf. or Provence.ti,ab,kf. or Provençal.ti,ab,kf. or

Lorraine.ti,ab,kf. or Lorrainian.ti,ab,kf. or Lorrainians.ti,ab,kf. or Picardy.ti,ab,kf. or Picard.ti,ab,kf. or Picards.ti,ab,kf. or Calais.ti,ab,kf. or Poitou-Charentes.ti,ab,kf. or Rhone-Alpes.ti,ab,kf. or Savoy.ti,ab,kf. or Savoyard.ti,ab,kf. or Savoyards.ti,ab,kf. or Austria.ti,ab,kf. or Austrian.ti,ab,kf. or Austrians.ti,ab,kf. or Vienna.ti,ab,kf. or Burgenland.ti,ab,kf. or Carinthia.ti,ab,kf. or Carinthian.ti,ab,kf. or Carinthians.ti,ab,kf. or Salzburger.ti,ab,kf. or Styria.ti,ab,kf. or Styrian.ti,ab,kf. or Styrians.ti,ab,kf. or Tyrol.ti,ab,kf. or Tyrolean.ti,ab,kf. or Tyroleans.ti,ab,kf. or Tyrolese.ti,ab,kf. or Vorarlberg.ti,ab,kf. or Germany.ti,ab,kf. or German.ti,ab,kf. or Berlin.ti,ab,kf. or Baden-Wurtemberg.ti,ab,kf. or Bavaria.ti,ab,kf. or Bavarian.ti,ab,kf. or Bavarians.ti,ab,kf. or Brandenburg.ti,ab,kf. or Bremen.ti,ab,kf. or Hamburg.ti,ab,kf. or Hesse.ti,ab,kf. or Hessian.ti,ab,kf. or Hessians.ti,ab,kf. or Holstein.ti,ab,kf. or Holsteinian.ti,ab,kf. or Holsteinians.ti,ab,kf. or Saxony.ti,ab,kf. or Saxon.ti,ab,kf. or Saxons.ti,ab,kf. or Mecklenburg.ti,ab,kf. or Westphalia.ti,ab,kf. or Westphalian.ti,ab,kf. or Westphalians.ti,ab,kf. or Palatinate.ti,ab,kf. or Palatine.ti,ab,kf. or Palatines.ti,ab,kf. or Saarland.ti,ab,kf. or Thuringia.ti,ab,kf. or Thuringian.ti,ab,kf. or Thuringians.ti,ab,kf. or Franconia.ti,ab,kf. or Franconian.ti,ab,kf. or Franconians.ti,ab,kf. or Lusatia.ti,ab,kf. or Lusatian.ti,ab,kf. or Lusatians.ti,ab,kf. or Rhineland.ti,ab,kf. or Rhenish.ti,ab,kf. or Rhinelanders.ti,ab,kf. or Switzerland.ti,ab,kf. or Swiss.ti,ab,kf. or Helvetian.ti,ab,kf. or Helvetians.ti,ab,kf. or Bern.ti,ab,kf. or Berne.ti,ab,kf. or Aargau.ti,ab,kf. or "Appenzell Ausserrhoden".ti,ab,kf. or Basel.ti,ab,kf. or Geneva.ti,ab,kf. or Glarus.ti,ab,kf. or Grisons.ti,ab,kf. or Jura.ti,ab,kf. or Lucerne.ti,ab,kf. or Neuchatel.ti,ab,kf. or Nidwalden.ti,ab,kf. or Obwalden.ti,ab,kf. or Schaffhausen.ti,ab,kf. or Schwyz.ti,ab,kf. or Solothurn.ti,ab,kf. or Gallen.ti,ab,kf. or Thurgau.ti,ab,kf. or Ticino.ti,ab,kf. or Tessin.ti,ab,kf. or Uri.ti,ab,kf. or Valais.ti,ab,kf. or Vaud.ti,ab,kf. or Zug.ti,ab,kf. or Zurich.ti,ab,kf. or Iceland.ti,ab,kf. or Icelander.ti,ab,kf. or Icelanders.ti,ab,kf. or Icelandic.ti,ab,kf. or Reykjavik.ti,ab,kf. or Ireland.ti,ab,kf. or Irish.ti,ab,kf. or Eire.ti,ab,kf. or Dublin.ti,ab,kf. or Kerry.ti,ab,kf. or Donegal.ti,ab,kf. or Connemara.ti,ab,kf. or Shannon.ti,ab,kf. or Aran.ti,ab,kf. or Celtic.ti,ab,kf. or Gaelic.ti,ab,kf. or "Great-Britain".ti,ab,kf. or "United Kingdom".ti,ab,kf. or British.ti,ab,kf. or London.ti,ab,kf. or England.ti,ab,kf. or English.ti,ab,kf. or Cornwall.ti,ab,kf. or Cornish.ti,ab,kf. or Scotland.ti,ab,kf. or Scottish.ti,ab,kf. or Wales.ti,ab,kf. or Welsh.ti,ab,kf. or Ulster.ti,ab,kf. or "Channel Islands".ti,ab,kf. or Guernsey.ti,ab,kf. or "Isle of Man".ti,ab,kf. or Orkney.ti,ab,kf. or Orcadian.ti,ab,kf. or Orcadians.ti,ab,kf. or Hebrides.ti,ab,kf. or Hebridean.ti,ab,kf. or Hebrideans.ti,ab,kf. or Shetland.ti,ab,kf. or Shetlanders.ti,ab,kf. or Cumbria.ti,ab,kf. or Cumbrian.ti,ab,kf. or Cumbrians.ti,ab,kf. or Fife.ti,ab,kf. or Fifers.ti,ab,kf. or Lancashire.ti,ab,kf. or Lancastrian.ti,ab,kf. or Lancastrians.ti,ab,kf. or Northumberland.ti,ab,kf. or Northumbria.ti,ab,kf. or Northumbrian.ti,ab,kf. or Northumbrians.ti,ab,kf. or Scandinavia.ti,ab,kf. or Scandinavian.ti,ab,kf. or Scandinavians.ti,ab,kf. or Denmark.ti,ab,kf. or Danish.ti,ab,kf. or Copenhagen.ti,ab,kf. or Jutland.ti,ab,kf. or Jutlanders.ti,ab,kf. or "Region-Zealand".ti,ab,kf. or Faeroe.ti,ab,kf. or Finland.ti,ab,kf. or Finnish.ti,ab,kf. or Finnic.ti,ab,kf. or Helsinki.ti,ab,kf. or Lapland.ti,ab,kf. or Lapp.ti,ab,kf. or Lappish.ti,ab,kf. or Saami.ti,ab,kf. or Saamis.ti,ab,kf. or Ostrobothnia.ti,ab,kf. or Kainuu.ti,ab,kf. or Savo.ti,ab,kf. or Pirkanmaa.ti,ab,kf. or Satakunta.ti,ab,kf. or Pajjat-Hame.ti,ab,kf. or Kanta-Hame.ti,ab,kf. or Kymenlaakso.ti,ab,kf. or Uusimaa.ti,ab,kf. or Aland.ti,ab,kf. or Norway.ti,ab,kf. or Norwegian.ti,ab,kf. or Norwegians.ti,ab,kf. or Oslo.ti,ab,kf. or Svalbard.ti,ab,kf. or "Jan Mayen".ti,ab,kf. or Troms.ti,ab,kf. or Nordland.ti,ab,kf. or Trondelag.ti,ab,kf. or Romsdal.ti,ab,kf. or Rogaland.ti,ab,kf. or Agder.ti,ab,kf. or Vestfold.ti,ab,kf. or Viken.ti,ab,kf. or Innlandet.ti,ab,kf. or Lofoten.ti,ab,kf. or Sweden.ti,ab,kf. or Swedish.ti,ab,kf. or Stockholm.ti,ab,kf. or Gotland.ti,ab,kf. or Gotlanders.ti,ab,kf. or Oland.ti,ab,kf. or Scania.ti,ab,kf. or Scanian.ti,ab,kf. or

Scanians.ti,ab,kf. or Skane.ti,ab,kf. or Norrland.ti,ab,kf. or Svealand.ti,ab,kf. or Gotaland.ti,ab,kf. or Blekinge.ti,ab,kf. or Dalarna.ti,ab,kf. or Gavleborg.ti,ab,kf. or Uppsala.ti,ab,kf. or Halland.ti,ab,kf. or Jamtland.ti,ab,kf. or Jonkoping.ti,ab,kf. or Kalmar.ti,ab,kf. or Kronoberg.ti,ab,kf. or Norrbotten.ti,ab,kf. or Sodermanland.ti,ab,kf. or Varmland.ti,ab,kf. or Vasterbotten.ti,ab,kf. or Vasternorrland.ti,ab,kf. or Vastmanland.ti,ab,kf. or Vastra.ti,ab,kf. or Orebro.ti,ab,kf. or Ostergotland.ti,ab,kf. or Netherland*.ti,ab,kf. or Holland.ti,ab,kf. or Amsterdam.ti,ab,kf. or Zeeland.ti,ab,kf. or Zeelanders.ti,ab,kf. or Friesland.ti,ab,kf. or Friesian.ti,ab,kf. or Friesians.ti,ab,kf. or Frisian.ti,ab,kf. or Frisians.ti,ab,kf. or Drenthe.ti,ab,kf. or Gelderland.ti,ab,kf. or Flevoland.ti,ab,kf. or Limburg.ti,ab,kf. or Noord-Brabant.ti,ab,kf. or Overijssel.ti,ab,kf. or Utrecht.ti,ab,kf. or Belgium.ti,ab,kf. or Belgian.ti,ab,kf. or Belgians.ti,ab,kf. or Brussels.ti,ab,kf. or Flanders.ti,ab,kf. or Flemish.ti,ab,kf. or Flemings.ti,ab,kf. or Wallonia.ti,ab,kf. or Walloon.ti,ab,kf. or Walloons.ti,ab,kf. or Luxembourg*.ti,ab,kf. 2799797

81 exp Epidemiologic Research Design/ or exp Epidemiologic Studies/ or exp Observational Studies/ or (case* adj5 control*).ti,ab,kf. or (case adj3 comparison*).ti,ab,kf. or (control adj1 group*).ti,ab,kf. or cohort.ti,ab,kf. or longitudinal.ti,ab,kf. or prospective.ti,ab,kf. or (association adj2 (studies or study)).ti,ab,kf. or (cross-sectional or prevalence or transversal).ti,ab,kf. or (association or associations).ti,ab,kf. or exp Incidence/ or (incidence or incidences).ti,ab,kf. or exp Prevalence/ or (prevalence or prevalences).ti,ab,kf. 7603519

82 18 and 79 and 80 and 81 5932

83 limit 82 to yr="2000 - 2024" 4722

84 limit 83 to english 4298

2. Embase

Search run on 2024-05-23

Embase

Session Results

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No.	Query Results	Results	Date
#85.	#84 AND ([embase]/lim OR [preprint]/lim)	5,855	23 May 2024
#84.	#18 AND #77 AND #80 AND #81 AND [2000-2024]/py AND [english]/lim	6,597	23 May 2024
#83.	#18 AND #77 AND #80 AND #81 AND [2000-2024]/py	6,969	23 May 2024
#82.	#18 AND #77 AND #80 AND #81	7,801	23 May 2024
#81.	'epidemiology'/exp OR 'observational study'/exp OR 'incidence'/exp OR 'prevalence'/exp OR ((case* NEAR/5 control*):ti,ab,kw) OR ((case NEAR/3 comparison*):ti,ab,kw) OR ((control NEAR/1 group*):ti,ab,kw) OR cohort:ti,ab,kw OR longitudinal:ti,ab,kw OR prospective:ti,ab,kw OR ((association NEAR/2 (studies OR study)):ti,ab,kw) OR 'cross sectional':ti,ab,kw OR transversal:ti,ab,kw OR association:ti,ab,kw OR associations:ti,ab,kw OR incidence:ti,ab,kw OR incidences:ti,ab,kw OR prevalence:ti,ab,kw OR	9,898,602	23 May 2024

prevalences:ti,ab,kw

#80. #78 OR #79

3,845,087 23 May 2024

#79. europe:ti,ab,kw OR european:ti,ab,kw OR

2,953,343 23 May 2024

europeans:ti,ab,kw OR 'alpine region*':ti,ab,kw

OR 'alpine area*':ti,ab,kw OR 'alpine

countr*':ti,ab,kw OR baltic:ti,ab,kw OR

baltics:ti,ab,kw OR balts:ti,ab,kw OR

estonia:ti,ab,kw OR estonian:ti,ab,kw OR

estonians:ti,ab,kw OR tallinn:ti,ab,kw OR

latvia:ti,ab,kw OR latvian:ti,ab,kw OR

latvians:ti,ab,kw OR letts:ti,ab,kw OR

riga:ti,ab,kw OR courland:ti,ab,kw OR

curonian:ti,ab,kw OR curonians:ti,ab,kw OR

lithuania:ti,ab,kw OR lithuanian:ti,ab,kw OR

lithuanians:ti,ab,kw OR vilnius:ti,ab,kw OR

poland:ti,ab,kw OR polish:ti,ab,kw OR

polska:ti,ab,kw OR warsaw:ti,ab,kw OR

warszaw:ti,ab,kw OR lemko:ti,ab,kw OR

lemkos:ti,ab,kw OR lemkan:ti,ab,kw OR

lemkians:ti,ab,kw OR lemki:ti,ab,kw OR

lemks:ti,ab,kw OR pomerania:ti,ab,kw OR

pomeranian:ti,ab,kw OR pomeranians:ti,ab,kw OR

silesia:ti,ab,kw OR silesian:ti,ab,kw OR

silesians:ti,ab,kw OR moravia:ti,ab,kw OR

moravian:ti,ab,kw OR moravians:ti,ab,kw OR

bulgaria:ti,ab,kw OR bulgarian:ti,ab,kw OR

bulgarians:ti,ab,kw OR sofia:ti,ab,kw OR

thrace:ti,ab,kw OR thracian:ti,ab,kw OR

thracians:ti,ab,kw OR romania:ti,ab,kw OR

romanian:ti,ab,kw OR romanians:ti,ab,kw OR

rumania:ti,ab,kw OR rumanian:ti,ab,kw OR

rumanians:ti,ab,kw OR bucharest:ti,ab,kw OR

bucuresti:ti,ab,kw OR transylvania:ti,ab,kw OR

transylvanian:ti,ab,kw OR transylvanians:ti,ab,kw

OR transilvania:ti,ab,kw OR

transilvanian:ti,ab,kw OR transilvanians:ti,ab,kw

OR wallachia:ti,ab,kw OR wallachian:ti,ab,kw OR

wallachians:ti,ab,kw OR hungary:ti,ab,kw OR

hungarian:ti,ab,kw OR hungarians:ti,ab,kw OR

magyar:ti,ab,kw OR magyars:ti,ab,kw OR

budapest:ti,ab,kw OR swabia:ti,ab,kw OR

swabian:ti,ab,kw OR swabians:ti,ab,kw OR

slovakia:ti,ab,kw OR slovak:ti,ab,kw OR

slovaks:ti,ab,kw OR slovakian:ti,ab,kw OR

slovakians:ti,ab,kw OR bratislava:ti,ab,kw OR

czech:ti,ab,kw OR czechia:ti,ab,kw OR

czechs:ti,ab,kw OR bohemia:ti,ab,kw OR

bohemian:ti,ab,kw OR bohemians:ti,ab,kw OR

prague:ti,ab,kw OR slovenia:ti,ab,kw OR
slovenian:ti,ab,kw OR slovenians:ti,ab,kw OR
ljubljana:ti,ab,kw OR balkan:ti,ab,kw OR
balkans:ti,ab,kw OR balkanic:ti,ab,kw OR
croatia:ti,ab,kw OR croatian:ti,ab,kw OR
croatians:ti,ab,kw OR dalmatia:ti,ab,kw OR
dalmatian:ti,ab,kw OR dalmatians:ti,ab,kw OR
istria:ti,ab,kw OR istrian:ti,ab,kw OR
istrians:ti,ab,kw OR zagreb:ti,ab,kw OR
greece:ti,ab,kw OR greek:ti,ab,kw OR
greeks:ti,ab,kw OR hellenic:ti,ab,kw OR
athens:ti,ab,kw OR crete:ti,ab,kw OR
cretan:ti,ab,kw OR cretans:ti,ab,kw OR
cyclades:ti,ab,kw OR cycladic:ti,ab,kw OR
dodecanese:ti,ab,kw OR dodecanesian:ti,ab,kw OR
peloponnese:ti,ab,kw OR peloponnesian:ti,ab,kw OR
peloponnesians:ti,ab,kw OR cyprus:ti,ab,kw OR
cypriot:ti,ab,kw OR cypriots:ti,ab,kw OR
cypriotic:ti,ab,kw OR cypriote:ti,ab,kw OR
nicosia:ti,ab,kw OR malta:ti,ab,kw OR
maltese:ti,ab,kw OR valetta:ti,ab,kw OR
valletta:ti,ab,kw OR gozo:ti,ab,kw OR
gozitan:ti,ab,kw OR gozitans:ti,ab,kw OR
portugal:ti,ab,kw OR portuguese:ti,ab,kw OR
portugueses:ti,ab,kw OR lisbon:ti,ab,kw OR
madeira:ti,ab,kw OR madeiran:ti,ab,kw OR
madeirans:ti,ab,kw OR azores:ti,ab,kw OR
azorean:ti,ab,kw OR azoreans:ti,ab,kw OR
macaronesia:ti,ab,kw OR macaronesian:ti,ab,kw OR
macaronesians:ti,ab,kw OR alentejo:ti,ab,kw OR
algarve:ti,ab,kw OR spain:ti,ab,kw OR
spanish:ti,ab,kw OR iberian:ti,ab,kw OR
iberians:ti,ab,kw OR madrid:ti,ab,kw OR
balearic:ti,ab,kw OR majorca:ti,ab,kw OR
majorcan:ti,ab,kw OR majorcans:ti,ab,kw OR
mallorca:ti,ab,kw OR mallorcan:ti,ab,kw OR
mallorcans:ti,ab,kw OR menorca:ti,ab,kw OR
menorcan:ti,ab,kw OR menorcans:ti,ab,kw OR
canary:ti,ab,kw OR canarian:ti,ab,kw OR
canarians:ti,ab,kw OR andalusia:ti,ab,kw OR
andalusian:ti,ab,kw OR andalusians:ti,ab,kw OR
murcia:ti,ab,kw OR murcian:ti,ab,kw OR
murcians:ti,ab,kw OR valencia:ti,ab,kw OR
valencian:ti,ab,kw OR valencians:ti,ab,kw OR
castilla:ti,ab,kw OR castile:ti,ab,kw OR
castilian:ti,ab,kw OR castilians:ti,ab,kw OR
castillian:ti,ab,kw OR castillians:ti,ab,kw OR
leon:ti,ab,kw OR leonese:ti,ab,kw OR

leoneses:ti,ab,kw OR extremadura:ti,ab,kw OR
extremaduran:ti,ab,kw OR extremadurans:ti,ab,kw
OR catalonia:ti,ab,kw OR catalan:ti,ab,kw OR
catalans:ti,ab,kw OR aragon:ti,ab,kw OR
aragones:ti,ab,kw OR navarre:ti,ab,kw OR
navarran:ti,ab,kw OR navarrans:ti,ab,kw OR
basque:ti,ab,kw OR basques:ti,ab,kw OR
cantabria:ti,ab,kw OR cantabric:ti,ab,kw OR
cantabrian:ti,ab,kw OR cantabrians:ti,ab,kw OR
asturias:ti,ab,kw OR asturian:ti,ab,kw OR
asturians:ti,ab,kw OR galicia:ti,ab,kw OR
galician:ti,ab,kw OR galicians:ti,ab,kw OR
pyrenees:ti,ab,kw OR pyreanean:ti,ab,kw OR
gibraltar:ti,ab,kw OR gibraltarian:ti,ab,kw OR
gibraltarians:ti,ab,kw OR italy:ti,ab,kw OR
italian:ti,ab,kw OR italians:ti,ab,kw OR
rome:ti,ab,kw OR apennine:ti,ab,kw OR
padane:ti,ab,kw OR sicily:ti,ab,kw OR
sicilian:ti,ab,kw OR sicilians:ti,ab,kw OR
sardinia:ti,ab,kw OR sardinian:ti,ab,kw OR
sardinians:ti,ab,kw OR aosta:ti,ab,kw OR
trentino:ti,ab,kw OR piedmont:ti,ab,kw OR
piedmontese:ti,ab,kw OR liguria:ti,ab,kw OR
ligurian:ti,ab,kw OR ligurians:ti,ab,kw OR
lombardy:ti,ab,kw OR lombard:ti,ab,kw OR
lombards:ti,ab,kw OR lombardic:ti,ab,kw OR
veneto:ti,ab,kw OR venetian:ti,ab,kw OR
venetians:ti,ab,kw OR friuli:ti,ab,kw OR 'emilia
romagna':ti,ab,kw OR emilian:ti,ab,kw OR
tuscany:ti,ab,kw OR tuscan:ti,ab,kw OR
tuscan:ti,ab,kw OR umbria:ti,ab,kw OR
umbrian:ti,ab,kw OR umbrians:ti,ab,kw OR
marche:ti,ab,kw OR latium:ti,ab,kw OR
abruzzo:ti,ab,kw OR molise:ti,ab,kw OR
campania:ti,ab,kw OR campanian:ti,ab,kw OR
campanians:ti,ab,kw OR apulia:ti,ab,kw OR
apulian:ti,ab,kw OR apulians:ti,ab,kw OR
basilicata:ti,ab,kw OR calabria:ti,ab,kw OR
calabrian:ti,ab,kw OR calabrians:ti,ab,kw OR
france:ti,ab,kw OR french:ti,ab,kw OR
paris:ti,ab,kw OR corsica:ti,ab,kw OR
corsican:ti,ab,kw OR corsicans:ti,ab,kw OR
alsace:ti,ab,kw OR alsatian:ti,ab,kw OR
alsatians:ti,ab,kw OR aquitaine:ti,ab,kw OR
aquitain:ti,ab,kw OR aquitan:ti,ab,kw OR
aquitans:ti,ab,kw OR occitan:ti,ab,kw OR
occitans:ti,ab,kw OR auvergne:ti,ab,kw OR
auvergnese:ti,ab,kw OR brittany:ti,ab,kw OR

bretagne:ti,ab,kw OR breton:ti,ab,kw OR
bretons:ti,ab,kw OR burgundy:ti,ab,kw OR
burgundian:ti,ab,kw OR burgundians:ti,ab,kw OR
loire:ti,ab,kw OR ardenne:ti,ab,kw OR
normandy:ti,ab,kw OR norman:ti,ab,kw OR
normans:ti,ab,kw OR 'franche comte':ti,ab,kw OR
'languedoc roussillon':ti,ab,kw OR
limousin:ti,ab,kw OR azur:ti,ab,kw OR
provence:ti,ab,kw OR provencal:ti,ab,kw OR
lorraine:ti,ab,kw OR lorrainian:ti,ab,kw OR
lorrainians:ti,ab,kw OR picardy:ti,ab,kw OR
picard:ti,ab,kw OR picards:ti,ab,kw OR
calais:ti,ab,kw OR 'poitou charentes':ti,ab,kw OR
'rhone alpes':ti,ab,kw OR savoy:ti,ab,kw OR
savoyard:ti,ab,kw OR savoyards:ti,ab,kw OR
austria:ti,ab,kw OR austrian:ti,ab,kw OR
austrians:ti,ab,kw OR vienna:ti,ab,kw OR
burgenland:ti,ab,kw OR carinthia:ti,ab,kw OR
carinthian:ti,ab,kw OR carinthians:ti,ab,kw OR
salzburger:ti,ab,kw OR styria:ti,ab,kw OR
styrian:ti,ab,kw OR styrians:ti,ab,kw OR
tyrol:ti,ab,kw OR tyrolean:ti,ab,kw OR
tyroleans:ti,ab,kw OR tyrolese:ti,ab,kw OR
vorarlberg:ti,ab,kw OR germany:ti,ab,kw OR
german:ti,ab,kw OR berlin:ti,ab,kw OR 'baden
wurttemberg':ti,ab,kw OR bavaria:ti,ab,kw OR
bavarian:ti,ab,kw OR bavarians:ti,ab,kw OR
brandenburg:ti,ab,kw OR bremen:ti,ab,kw OR
hamburg:ti,ab,kw OR hesse:ti,ab,kw OR
hessian:ti,ab,kw OR hessians:ti,ab,kw OR
holstein:ti,ab,kw OR holsteinian:ti,ab,kw OR
holsteinians:ti,ab,kw OR saxony:ti,ab,kw OR
saxon:ti,ab,kw OR saxons:ti,ab,kw OR
mecklenburg:ti,ab,kw OR westphalia:ti,ab,kw OR
westphalian:ti,ab,kw OR westphalians:ti,ab,kw OR
palatinate:ti,ab,kw OR palatine:ti,ab,kw OR
palatines:ti,ab,kw OR saarland:ti,ab,kw OR
thuringia:ti,ab,kw OR thuringian:ti,ab,kw OR
thuringians:ti,ab,kw OR franconia:ti,ab,kw OR
franconian:ti,ab,kw OR franconians:ti,ab,kw OR
lusatia:ti,ab,kw OR lusatian:ti,ab,kw OR
lusatians:ti,ab,kw OR rhineland:ti,ab,kw OR
rhenish:ti,ab,kw OR rhinelanders:ti,ab,kw OR
switzerland:ti,ab,kw OR swiss:ti,ab,kw OR
helvetian:ti,ab,kw OR helvetians:ti,ab,kw OR
bern:ti,ab,kw OR berne:ti,ab,kw OR
aargau:ti,ab,kw OR 'appenzell
ausserrhoden':ti,ab,kw OR basel:ti,ab,kw OR

geneva:ti,ab,kw OR glarus:ti,ab,kw OR
grisons:ti,ab,kw OR jura:ti,ab,kw OR
lucerne:ti,ab,kw OR neuchatel:ti,ab,kw OR
nidwalden:ti,ab,kw OR obwalden:ti,ab,kw OR
schaffhausen:ti,ab,kw OR schwyz:ti,ab,kw OR
solothurn:ti,ab,kw OR gallen:ti,ab,kw OR
thurgau:ti,ab,kw OR ticino:ti,ab,kw OR
tessin:ti,ab,kw OR uri:ti,ab,kw OR
valais:ti,ab,kw OR vaud:ti,ab,kw OR zug:ti,ab,kw
OR zurich:ti,ab,kw OR iceland:ti,ab,kw OR
icelander:ti,ab,kw OR icelanders:ti,ab,kw OR
icelandic:ti,ab,kw OR reykjavik:ti,ab,kw OR
ireland:ti,ab,kw OR irish:ti,ab,kw OR
eire:ti,ab,kw OR dublin:ti,ab,kw OR
kerry:ti,ab,kw OR donegal:ti,ab,kw OR
connemara:ti,ab,kw OR shannon:ti,ab,kw OR
aran:ti,ab,kw OR celtic:ti,ab,kw OR
gaelic:ti,ab,kw OR 'great-britain':ti,ab,kw OR
'united kingdom':ti,ab,kw OR british:ti,ab,kw OR
london:ti,ab,kw OR england:ti,ab,kw OR
english:ti,ab,kw OR cornwall:ti,ab,kw OR
cornish:ti,ab,kw OR scotland:ti,ab,kw OR
scottish:ti,ab,kw OR wales:ti,ab,kw OR
welsh:ti,ab,kw OR ulster:ti,ab,kw OR 'channel
islands':ti,ab,kw OR guernsey:ti,ab,kw OR 'isle
of man':ti,ab,kw OR orkney:ti,ab,kw OR
orcadian:ti,ab,kw OR orcadians:ti,ab,kw OR
hebrides:ti,ab,kw OR hebridean:ti,ab,kw OR
hebrideans:ti,ab,kw OR shetland:ti,ab,kw OR
shetlanders:ti,ab,kw OR cumbria:ti,ab,kw OR
cumbrian:ti,ab,kw OR cumbrians:ti,ab,kw OR
fife:ti,ab,kw OR fifers:ti,ab,kw OR
lancashire:ti,ab,kw OR lancastrian:ti,ab,kw OR
lancastrians:ti,ab,kw OR northumberland:ti,ab,kw
OR northumbria:ti,ab,kw OR northumbrian:ti,ab,kw
OR northumbrians:ti,ab,kw OR scandinavia:ti,ab,kw
OR scandinavian:ti,ab,kw OR
scandinavians:ti,ab,kw OR denmark:ti,ab,kw OR
danish:ti,ab,kw OR copenhagen:ti,ab,kw OR
jutland:ti,ab,kw OR jutlanders:ti,ab,kw OR
'region-zealand':ti,ab,kw OR faeroe:ti,ab,kw OR
finland:ti,ab,kw OR finnish:ti,ab,kw OR
finnic:ti,ab,kw OR helsinki:ti,ab,kw OR
lapland:ti,ab,kw OR lapp:ti,ab,kw OR
lappish:ti,ab,kw OR saami:ti,ab,kw OR
saamis:ti,ab,kw OR ostrobothnia:ti,ab,kw OR
kainuu:ti,ab,kw OR savo:ti,ab,kw OR
pirkanmaa:ti,ab,kw OR satakunta:ti,ab,kw OR

'paijat hame':ti,ab,kw OR 'kanta hame':ti,ab,kw
OR kymenlaakso:ti,ab,kw OR uusimaa:ti,ab,kw OR
aland:ti,ab,kw OR norway:ti,ab,kw OR
norwegian:ti,ab,kw OR norwegians:ti,ab,kw OR
oslo:ti,ab,kw OR svalbard:ti,ab,kw OR 'jan
mayen':ti,ab,kw OR troms:ti,ab,kw OR
nordland:ti,ab,kw OR trondelag:ti,ab,kw OR
romsdal:ti,ab,kw OR rogaland:ti,ab,kw OR
agder:ti,ab,kw OR vestfold:ti,ab,kw OR
viken:ti,ab,kw OR innlandet:ti,ab,kw OR
lofoten:ti,ab,kw OR sweden:ti,ab,kw OR
swedish:ti,ab,kw OR stockholm:ti,ab,kw OR
gotland:ti,ab,kw OR gotlanders:ti,ab,kw OR
oland:ti,ab,kw OR scania:ti,ab,kw OR
scanian:ti,ab,kw OR scanians:ti,ab,kw OR
skane:ti,ab,kw OR norrland:ti,ab,kw OR
svealand:ti,ab,kw OR gotaland:ti,ab,kw OR
blekinge:ti,ab,kw OR dalarna:ti,ab,kw OR
gavleborg:ti,ab,kw OR uppsala:ti,ab,kw OR
halland:ti,ab,kw OR jamtland:ti,ab,kw OR
jonkoping:ti,ab,kw OR kalmar:ti,ab,kw OR
kronoberg:ti,ab,kw OR norrbotten:ti,ab,kw OR
sodermanland:ti,ab,kw OR varmland:ti,ab,kw OR
vasterbotten:ti,ab,kw OR vasternorrland:ti,ab,kw
OR vastmanland:ti,ab,kw OR vastra:ti,ab,kw OR
orebro:ti,ab,kw OR ostergotland:ti,ab,kw OR
netherlands*:ti,ab,kw OR holland:ti,ab,kw OR
amsterdam:ti,ab,kw OR zeeland:ti,ab,kw OR
zeelanders:ti,ab,kw OR friesland:ti,ab,kw OR
friesian:ti,ab,kw OR friesland:ti,ab,kw OR
frisian:ti,ab,kw OR frisians:ti,ab,kw OR
drenthe:ti,ab,kw OR gelderland:ti,ab,kw OR
flevoland:ti,ab,kw OR limburg:ti,ab,kw OR 'noord
brabant':ti,ab,kw OR overijssel:ti,ab,kw OR
utrecht:ti,ab,kw OR belgium:ti,ab,kw OR
belgian:ti,ab,kw OR belgians:ti,ab,kw OR
brussels:ti,ab,kw OR flanders:ti,ab,kw OR
flemish:ti,ab,kw OR flemings:ti,ab,kw OR
wallonia:ti,ab,kw OR walloon:ti,ab,kw OR
walloons:ti,ab,kw OR luxembourg*:ti,ab,kw

#78. 'europe'/exp OR 'european'/exp

2,101,309 23 May 2024

#77. #19 OR #20 OR #21 OR #22 OR #23 OR #24 OR #25 OR

9,490,653 23 May 2024

#26 OR #27 OR #28 OR #29 OR #30 OR #31 OR #32 OR
#33 OR #34 OR #35 OR #36 OR #37 OR #38 OR #39 OR
#40 OR #41 OR #42 OR #43 OR #44 OR #45 OR #46 OR
#47 OR #48 OR #49 OR #50 OR #51 OR #52 OR #53 OR
#54 OR #55 OR #56 OR #57 OR #58 OR #59 OR #60 OR
#61 OR #62 OR #63 OR #64 OR #65 OR #66 OR #67 OR

#68 OR #69 OR #70 OR #71 OR #72 OR #73 OR #74 OR
#75 OR #76

#76. ((higher OR better OR worse OR less) NEAR/2 49,472 23 May 2024
(educated OR education)):ti,ab,kw

#75. (school* NEAR/1 duration*):ti,ab,kw 66 23 May 2024

#74. schooling:ti,ab,kw OR illiterate:ti,ab,kw OR 19,633 23 May 2024
uneducated:ti,ab,kw

#73. (household NEAR/2 size):ti,ab,kw 2,433 23 May 2024

#72. homeless*:ti,ab,kw OR foreclosure*:ti,ab,kw OR 20,010 23 May 2024
eviction*:ti,ab,kw

#71. ((residential OR neighbo?rhood) NEAR/2 2,240 23 May 2024
environment*):ti,ab,kw

#70. ((urban OR rural OR inner*city OR slum OR 10,545 23 May 2024
neighbo?rhood) NEAR/2 (difference* OR specific OR
analysis OR inequit* OR disparit* OR inequalit*
OR depriv* OR disadvantage*)):ti,ab,kw

#69. housing:ti,ab,kw 48,224 23 May 2024

#68. 'homeless person'/exp 4,201 23 May 2024

#67. 'home environment'/exp 7,310 23 May 2024

#66. 'built environment'/exp 2,219 23 May 2024

#65. 'residence characteristics'/exp 3,755 23 May 2024

#64. ((marriage OR marital OR civil) NEAR/1 42,249 23 May 2024
status):ti,ab,kw

#63. ((social* OR socio* OR psychosocial) NEAR/2 347,719 23 May 2024
(advantage* OR disadvantage* OR exclude* OR
exclusion OR include* OR inclusion OR status OR
position OR gradient* OR hierarch* OR class* OR
determinant* OR discrimin* OR condition OR
network* OR connection OR relation* OR capital OR
cohes* OR organis* OR organiz* OR context OR
support OR influence)):ti,ab,kw

#62. 'social environment'/exp 683,750 23 May 2024

#61. 'social control'/exp 436,385 23 May 2024

#60. 'social capital'/exp 4,264 23 May 2024

#59. 'social stigma'/exp 17,135 23 May 2024

#58. 'socio economic*':ti,ab,kw OR economic*':ti,ab,kw 3,552,801 23 May 2024
OR poverty:ti,ab,kw OR poor*':ti,ab,kw OR
income:ti,ab,kw OR socioeconomic*':ti,ab,kw OR
socio?economic*':ti,ab,kw OR occupation*':ti,ab,kw
OR employ*':ti,ab,kw OR unemploy*':ti,ab,kw OR
impoverished:ti,ab,kw

#57. 'social dominance'/exp 6,880 23 May 2024

#56. 'social hierarchy'/exp 9,159 23 May 2024

#55. 'social welfare'/exp 23,961 23 May 2024

#54. 'job description':ti,ab,kw 1,091 23 May 2024

#53. 'socioeconomics'/exp 1,570,486 23 May 2024

#52. ethnic*':ti,ab,kw OR race:ti,ab,kw OR 2,814,507 23 May 2024
racial:ti,ab,kw OR religio*':ti,ab,kw OR

cultur*:ti,ab,kw OR minorit*:ti,ab,kw OR
 refugee*:ti,ab,kw OR refugi*:ti,ab,kw OR
 indigenous:ti,ab,kw OR migrant*:ti,ab,kw OR
 immigr*:ti,ab,kw OR racism:ti,ab,kw OR
 transient*:ti,ab,kw

#51. 'religion'/exp	87,041	23 May 2024
#50. disabled:ti,ab,kw OR disabilit*:ti,ab,kw OR handicap*:ti,ab,kw	422,756	23 May 2024
#49. 'disabled person'/exp	66,027	23 May 2024
#48. 'cultural diversity'/exp	4,655	23 May 2024
#47. 'cultural factor'/exp	70,140	23 May 2024
#46. 'social isolation'/exp	36,066	23 May 2024
#45. 'desegregation'/exp	66	23 May 2024
#44. 'apartheid'/exp	125	23 May 2024
#43. 'race relation'/exp	17,350	23 May 2024
#42. 'refugee'/exp	18,711	23 May 2024
#41. 'ancestry group'/exp	459,242	23 May 2024
#40. 'ethnicity'/exp	129,767	23 May 2024
#39. 'minority health'/exp	1,115	23 May 2024
#38. 'minority group'/exp	72,431	23 May 2024
#37. 'migration'/exp	53,839	23 May 2024
#36. 'ethnic group'/exp	231,915	23 May 2024
#35. 'vulnerable population'/exp	30,183	23 May 2024
#34. (m?n* NEAR/1 role):ti,ab,kw	2,787	23 May 2024
#33. ((wom?n* OR female*) NEAR/1 role):ti,ab,kw	589	23 May 2024
#32. gender:ti,ab,kw	691,575	23 May 2024
#31. (sex NEAR/2 (role OR difference? OR factor? OR inequit* OR disparit* OR inequalit*)):ti,ab,kw	84,981	23 May 2024
#30. 'gender based':ti,ab,kw OR 'gender related':ti,ab,kw OR 'gender differences':ti,ab,kw OR 'gender factors':ti,ab,kw	60,476	23 May 2024
#29. 'homosexuality'/exp	29,233	23 May 2024
#28. 'women`s health'/exp	34,932	23 May 2024
#27. 'gender identity'/exp	23,716	23 May 2024
#26. 'gender equity'/exp	2,141	23 May 2024
#25. 'sex'/exp	482,553	23 May 2024
#24. ((socio* OR social) NEAR/1 (determinant* OR differen* OR factor*)):ti,ab,kw	94,326	23 May 2024
#23. inequit*:ti,ab,kw OR disparit*:ti,ab,kw OR inequalit*:ti,ab,kw OR disadvantage*:ti,ab,kw OR depriv*:ti,ab,kw OR vulnerab*:ti,ab,kw OR justice:ti,ab,kw OR injustice:ti,ab,kw OR equity:ti,ab,kw OR equality:ti,ab,kw	785,535	23 May 2024
#22. 'diversity, equity and inclusion'/exp	1,089	23 May 2024
#21. 'social determinants of health'/exp	23,540	23 May 2024
#20. 'health disparity'/exp	40,232	23 May 2024
#19. 'health equity'/exp	12,566	23 May 2024

#18. #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13 OR #14 OR #15 OR #16 OR #17	376,735	23 May 2024
#17. ((emission* OR air OR atmospher*) NEAR/2 (anthropogenic OR motor OR automobile* OR car OR cars OR road OR 'power generation' OR indust* OR combustion OR smelting OR construction OR demolition OR burning OR 'chemical plant' OR 'chemical plants' OR refiner* OR residential OR fire OR fires OR ship OR ships OR locomotive OR volcano OR incinerator OR smelter*)):ti,ab,kw	14,728	23 May 2024
#16. (smog:ti,ab,kw OR fume*:ti,ab,kw OR exhaust*:ti,ab,kw OR diesel:ti,ab,kw) AND air:ti,ab,kw	11,762	23 May 2024
#15. ((vehicle* OR traffic) NEAR/3 (emission* OR pollutant*)):ti,ab,kw	7,768	23 May 2024
#14. 'coarse particle':ti,ab,kw OR 'coarse particles':ti,ab,kw OR soot:ti,ab,kw OR 'black smoke':ti,ab,kw OR 'black carbon':ti,ab,kw OR 'elemental carbon':ti,ab,kw OR 'wood smoke':ti,ab,kw	15,156	23 May 2024
#13. fossil:ti,ab,kw AND fuel*:ti,ab,kw	10,078	23 May 2024
#12. so2:ti,ab,kw OR no2:ti,ab,kw OR o3:ti,ab,kw OR ozone:ti,ab,kw OR 'nitrogen dioxide':ti,ab,kw OR 'sulfur dioxide':ti,ab,kw OR 'carbon monoxide':ti,ab,kw	102,318	23 May 2024
#11. pm2*:ti,ab,kw OR pm10*:ti,ab,kw	15,021	23 May 2024
#10. ((air OR ambient OR atmospher*) NEAR/3 (pollut* OR quality)):ti,ab,kw	88,706	23 May 2024
#9. 'fossil fuel'/exp	7,772	23 May 2024
#8. 'carbon monoxide'/exp	47,441	23 May 2024
#7. 'sulfur dioxide'/exp	18,643	23 May 2024
#6. 'ozone'/exp	36,171	23 May 2024
#5. 'traffic pollution'/exp	591	23 May 2024
#4. 'exhaust gas'/exp	22,676	23 May 2024
#3. 'particulate matter'/exp	65,966	23 May 2024
#2. 'air pollutant'/exp	108,908	23 May 2024
#1. 'air pollution'/exp	221,763	23 May 2024

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3. Scopus

Search run on 3.6.2024

(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("air pollution" OR "air pollutants" OR "particulate matter" OR "vehicle emissions" OR ozone OR "sulfur dioxide" OR "carbon monoxide" OR "fossil fuels" OR "pm2.5" OR pm10 OR so2 OR no2 OR o3 OR ozone OR "nitrogen dioxide" OR "sulfur

dioxide" OR "carbon monoxide" OR "coarse particles" OR soot OR "black smoke" OR "black carbon" OR "elemental carbon" OR "wood smoke") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (traffic AND pollution) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((air OR ambient OR atmosphere OR atmospheric) AND (pollute OR polluted OR pollution OR quality)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((vehicle OR vehicles OR traffic) AND (emissions OR pollutant OR pollutants)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((smog OR fume OR fumes OR exhaust OR exhausts OR diesel) AND air) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((emissions OR air OR atmosphere OR atmospheric) AND (anthropogenic OR motor OR automobile OR automobiles OR car OR cars OR road OR "power generation" OR industry OR industrial OR combustion OR smelting OR construction OR demolition OR burning OR "chemical plant" OR "chemical plants" OR refinery OR refineries OR residential OR fire OR fires OR ship OR ships OR locomotive OR volcano OR incinerator OR smelter))) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (europe OR european OR europeans OR "alpine region" OR "alpine area**" OR "alpine countries" OR baltic OR baltics OR balts OR estonia OR estonian OR estonians OR tallinn OR latvia OR latvian OR latvians OR letts OR riga OR courland OR curonian OR curonians OR lithuania OR lithuanian OR lithuanians OR vilnius OR poland OR polish OR polska OR warsaw OR warszaw OR lemko OR lemkos OR lemkan OR lemkanians OR lemko OR lemks OR pomerania OR pomeranian OR pomeranians OR silesia OR silesian OR silesians OR moravia OR moravian OR moravians OR bulgaria OR bulgarian OR bulgarians OR sofia OR thrace OR thracian OR thracians OR romania OR romanian OR romanians OR rumania OR rumanian OR rumanians OR bucharest OR bucuresti OR transylvania OR transylvanian OR transylvanians OR transilvania OR transilvanian OR transilvanians OR wallachia OR wallachian OR wallachians OR hungary OR hungarian OR hungarians OR magyar OR magyars OR budapest OR swabia OR swabian OR swabians OR slovakia OR slovak OR slovaks OR slovakian OR slovakians OR bratislava OR czech OR czechia OR czechs OR bohemia OR bohemian OR bohemians OR prague OR slovenia OR slovenian OR slovenians OR ljubljana OR balkan OR balkans OR balkanic OR croatia OR croatian OR croatians OR dalmatia OR dalmatian OR dalmatians OR istria OR istrian OR istrians OR zagreb OR greece OR greek OR greeks OR hellenic OR athens OR crete OR cretan OR cretans OR cyclades OR cycladic OR dodecanese OR dodecanesian OR peloponnese OR peloponnesian OR peloponnesians OR cyprus OR cyriot OR cyriots OR cyriotic OR cyriote OR nicosia OR malta OR maltese OR valetta OR valletta OR gozo OR gozitan OR gozitans OR portugal OR portuguese OR portugueses OR lisbon OR madeira OR madeiran OR madeirans OR azores OR azorean OR azoreans OR macaronesia OR macaronesian OR macaronesians OR alentejo OR algarve OR spain OR spanish OR iberian OR iberians OR madrid OR balearic OR majorca OR majorcan OR majorcans OR mallorca OR mallorcan OR mallorcans OR menorca OR menorcan OR menorcans OR canary OR canarian OR canarians OR andalusia OR andalusian OR andalusians OR murcia OR murcian OR murcians OR valencia OR valencian OR valencians OR castilla OR castile OR castilian OR castilians OR castillian OR castillians OR leon OR leonese OR leoneses OR extremadura OR extremaduran OR extremadurans OR catalonia OR catalan OR catalans OR aragon OR aragonese OR navarre OR navarran OR navarrans OR basque OR basques OR cantabria OR cantabric OR cantabrian OR cantabrians OR asturias OR asturian OR asturians OR galicia OR galician OR galicians OR pyrenees OR pyrenean OR gibraltar OR gibraltarian OR gibraltarians OR italy OR italian OR italians OR rome OR apennine OR padane OR sicily OR sicilian OR sicilians OR sardinia OR sardinian OR sardinians OR aosta OR trentino OR piedmont OR piedmontese OR liguria OR ligurian OR ligurians OR lombardy OR lombard OR lombards OR lombardic OR veneto OR venetian OR venetians OR friuli OR "emilia romagna" OR emilian OR tuscany OR tuscan OR tuscans OR umbria OR umbrian

OR umbrians OR marche OR latium OR abruzzo OR molise OR campania OR campanian
OR campanians OR apulia OR apulian OR apulians OR basilicata OR calabria OR calabrian
OR calabrians OR france OR french OR paris OR corsica OR corsican OR corsicans OR
alsace OR alsatian OR alsatians OR aquitaine OR aquitain OR aquitan OR aquitans OR
occitan OR occitans OR auvergne OR auvergnese OR brittany OR bretagne OR breton OR
bretons OR burgundy OR burgundian OR burgundians OR loire OR ardenne OR normandy
OR norman OR normans OR "franche comte" OR "languedoc roussillon" OR limousin OR
azur OR provence OR provencal OR lorraine OR lorrainian OR lorrainians OR picardy OR
picard OR picards OR calais OR "poitou charentes" OR "rhone alpes" OR savoy OR
savoyard OR savoyards OR austria OR austrian OR austrians OR vienna OR burgenland
OR carinthia OR carinthian OR carinthians OR salzburger OR styria OR styrian OR styrians
OR tyrol OR tyrolean OR tyroleans OR tyrolese OR vorarlberg OR germany OR german OR
berlin OR "baden wurttemberg" OR bavaria OR bavarian OR bavarians OR brandenburg OR
bremen OR hamburg OR hesse OR hessian OR hessians OR holstein OR holsteinian OR
holsteinians OR saxony OR saxon OR saxons OR mecklenburg OR westphalia OR
westphalian OR westphalians OR palatinate OR palatine OR palatines OR saarland OR
thuringia OR thuringian OR thuringians OR franconia OR franconian OR franconians OR
lusatia OR lusatian OR lusatians OR rhineland OR rhenish OR rhinelanders OR switzerland
OR swiss OR helvetian OR helvetians OR bern OR berne OR aargau OR "appenzell
ausserrhoden" OR basel OR geneva OR glarus OR grisons OR jura OR lucerne OR
neuchatel OR nidwalden OR obwalden OR schaffhausen OR schwyz OR solothurn OR
gallen OR thurgau OR ticino OR tessin OR uri OR valais OR vaud OR zug OR zurich OR
iceland OR icelander OR icelanders OR icelandic OR reykjavik OR ireland OR irish OR eire
OR dublin OR kerry OR donegal OR connemara OR shannon OR aran OR celtic OR gaelic
OR "great-britain" OR "united kingdom" OR british OR london OR england OR english OR
cornwall OR cornish OR scotland OR scottish OR wales OR welsh OR ulster OR "channel
islands" OR guernsey OR "isle of man" OR orkney OR orcadian OR orcadians OR hebrides
OR hebridean OR hebrideans OR shetland OR shetlanders OR cumbria OR cumbrian OR
cumbrians OR fife OR fifers OR lancashire OR lancastrian OR lancastrians OR
northumberland OR northumbria OR northumbrian OR northumbrians OR scandinavia OR
scandinavian OR scandinavians OR denmark OR danish OR copenhagen OR jutland OR
jutlanders OR "region-zealand" OR faeroe OR finland OR finnish OR finnic OR helsinki OR
lapland OR lapp OR lappish OR saami OR saamis OR ostrobothnia OR kainuu OR savo OR
pirkanmaa OR satakunta OR "pajjat hame" OR "kanta hame" OR kymenlaakso OR uusimaa
OR aland OR norway OR norwegian OR norwegians OR oslo OR svalbard OR "jan mayen"
OR troms OR nordland OR trondelag OR romsdal OR rogaland OR agder OR vestfold OR
viken OR innlandet OR lofoten OR sweden OR swedish OR stockholm OR gotland OR
gotlanders OR oland OR scania OR scanian OR scanians OR skane OR norrland OR
svealand OR gotaland OR blekinge OR dalarna OR gavleborg OR uppsala OR halland OR
jamtland OR jonkoping OR kalmar OR kronoberg OR norrbotten OR sodermanland OR
varmland OR vasterbotten OR vasternorrland OR vastmanland OR vastra OR orebro OR
ostergotland OR netherlands* OR holland OR amsterdam OR zeeland OR zeelanders OR
friesland OR friesland OR friesland OR frisian OR frisians OR drenthe OR gelderland OR
flevoland OR limburg OR "noord brabant" OR overijssel OR utrecht OR belgium OR belgian
OR belgians OR brussels OR flanders OR flemish OR flemings OR wallonia OR walloon OR
walloons OR luxembourg)) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (epidemiology OR epidemiological OR
observational OR cohort OR longitudinal OR prospective OR cross-sectional OR prevalence
OR transversal OR association OR associations OR incidence OR incidences OR

prevalence OR prevalences) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("case control" OR "case controls") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("case comparison" OR "case comparisons") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("control group" OR "control groups")) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("women health" OR homosexuality OR gender OR apartheid OR desegregation OR "social isolation" OR acculturation OR "cross-cultural comparison" OR "cultural characteristics" OR "cultural diversity" OR "job description" OR "social welfare" OR "social hierarchy" OR "social dominance" OR "social stigma" OR "social capital" OR "social control" OR "social environment" OR "residence characteristics" OR "built environment" OR "home environment" OR "ill-housed persons" OR housing OR inequity OR inequities OR disparity OR disparities OR inequality OR inequalities OR disadvantage OR disadvantaged OR deprived OR deprivation OR vulnerable OR vulnerability OR justice OR injustice OR equity OR equality OR disabled OR disability OR disabilities OR handicap OR ethnic OR ethnicity OR race OR racial OR religion OR religions OR religious OR culture OR cultural OR minority OR minorities OR refugees OR indigenous OR migrant OR migrants OR immigration OR racism OR transient OR socio-economic OR economic OR poverty OR poor OR income OR occupation OR occupations OR employed OR employment OR unemployed OR unemployment OR impoverished) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (diversity AND inclusion) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((socio OR social) AND (determinant OR determinants OR different OR difference OR factor OR factors)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sex AND (role OR difference OR differences OR factor OR factors)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((woman OR women OR female) AND (role OR roles)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((man OR men) AND (role OR roles)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (health AND disparate AND vulnerable AND population) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((social OR socio OR psychosocial) AND (advantage OR advantaged OR disadvantage OR disadvantaged OR excluded OR exclusion OR included OR inclusion OR status OR position OR gradient OR gradients OR hierarchy OR hierarchies OR class OR classes OR determinants OR discrimination OR condition OR network OR networks OR connection OR relation OR relations OR capital OR cohesion OR organisation OR organization OR context OR support OR influence)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((marriage OR marital OR civil) AND status) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((urban OR rural OR inner-city OR slum OR neighborhood OR neighbourhood) AND (difference OR differences OR specific OR analysis OR inequity OR inequities OR disparity OR disparities OR inequality OR inequalities OR deprived OR deprivation OR disadvantage OR disadvantaged)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((residential OR neighborhood OR neighbourhood) AND environment) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (homeless OR foreclosure OR eviction OR evictions) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (household AND size) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (schooling OR illiterate OR uneducated) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (school AND duration) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ((higher OR better OR worse OR less) AND (educated OR education))) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "english")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE , "j"))